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SELF-CONTROL WITH A COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH TO TEACHING ECONOMIC STUDENTS

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Abstract

In higher education, the control of educational activity is a check of the level of mastering of the curriculum by the student, and self-control is the ability of the student to check his acquired knowledge and make adjustments.

Practice shows that specialists who have a high ability to self-improvement and search for new effective forms of organizing their work are more in demand in the labor market. To do this, it is necessary to form self-control skills among students of economic universities in the process of studying at the university. It is necessary to actively involve, in the management of their educational process. This will allow you to believe in yourself, in your abilities, take a critical approach to learning outcomes and develop creatively. The article raises the current problem of developing students' self-control skills. The author analyzed the functions of self-control in the student's independent work. The conditions under which the skills of self-control of educational activities of students of economic specialties are formed in the process of their professional training are considered.

Keywords: control, self-control; educational activities; pedagogical conditions; training future economists.

Today, the education system does not stand still and is constantly being improved. The reason for this is the general technological revolution and the involvement of society in global processes, which in turn entail an increase in demand for competitive specialists in various fields of activity [1].

In this regard, the meaning and goals of pedagogical control are changing as a mechanism responsible for the continuous process of improving the quality of education and providing feedback between the subjects of the learning process. In the new conditions, pedagogical control, summing up the achievements of students, should become the starting point for the next stage of development and a new level of quality of education. Consequently, not only test and assessment materials must change, but also the goals of testing students' knowledge, skills and abilities and the philosophy of control itself.

Pedagogical control, as a component of the entire educational process, affects not only the result, but also

the entire process of training and education, since based on the analysis of control results, one can judge the effectiveness of the educational process and develop ways to further improve the entire educational process. Thus, issues of monitoring and assessing the development of competencies remain significant problems for pedagogical science and practice.

Today, the training of specialists in the higher education system has made a transition to multi-level training, focusing on a competency-based approach to training, providing for professional growth, social mobility and self-improvement of personnel.

In this regard, the meaning and goals of pedagogical control are changing as a mechanism responsible for the continuous process of improving the quality of education and providing feedback between the subjects of the learning process. In the new conditions, pedagogical control, summing up the achievements of students, should become the starting point for the next stage of development and a new level of quality of education.

Consequently, control and assessment materials for testing students' knowledge, skills and abilities in the vocational education system must change.

The main difficulty of assessment and control in a competency-based education system is that competencies are manifested only in the activities of students: completing projects; solving problem situations; solving problems that require a combination of knowledge and experience in combination with the personal characteristics of the student. This means that teachers need to introduce new control methods into the learning process and be aware of the peculiarities of its organization.

Control and measurement activities in the educational process establish not only the achievement of learning goals, but also the goals of education, that is, the development of personal qualities, which is difficult to define. In this regard, carrying out control and measurement activities or pedagogical control comes down to assessing the level of knowledge.

So, V.P. Arkhangelsky distinguishes input and output control, which perform certain tasks and have their own characteristics. In this case, the role of control is clearly specified, but the procedure for conducting control as a means of obtaining feedback is not specified [4].

Yu.K. Babansky argues that control is just one of the elements of learning built into the model of the educational process [5].

I.N. Kovalevsky believes that control tasks can change, i.e. Monitoring the results of education can be carried out both for preventive purposes and for the purpose of learning how to manage the learning process. Monitoring of current educational activities is carried out, first of all, to obtain feedback and check the intermediate educational achievements of students [6].

Hence, it can be argued that the essence of control is to receive feedback during the educational process, to establish compliance of the level of its results with the educational standard of the corresponding direction.

In higher education institutions, the teacher monitors and analyzes the student's activities. At the same time, the student receives an unreasoned mark on his activities. An incomplete assessment of the teacher and the student's inability to self-control, introspection and self-assessment of his activities disorients the student in assessing his own capabilities and forms an inadequate self-assessment of learning results.

Independent work, becoming increasingly important in the educational process, forms readiness for self-education and creates the basis for continuous improvement of one's qualifications. This is due to the fact that despite the fact that there is an increase in the disciplines studied by students, the time budget for classroom training is decreasing, and students have to study most of the course materials on their own in a short time. That is, there is a lack of time to master the volume of educational and scientific material required, according to the program.

To develop students' self-organization skills for studying at a university means learning to plan their educational and professional activities, effectively using

free time, being able to process large amounts of information, analyzing them, learning to clearly formulate their thoughts, and being able to work with people. Therefore, the focus of universities on developing students' ability to work independently is completely justified.

Curricula in universities today are formed taking into account a significant part of the workload of teachers allocated to independent work of students. Self-study, self-education, self-realization, self-control, self-esteem are necessary conditions for successfully completing the educational process. In addition, the direction of professional training at a university becomes practice-oriented and, consequently, the role of independent activity of students increases. The level of self-control becomes the main criterion of a specialist's professional literacy.

The main aspect of a student's educational work is the control and evaluation of his activities, when the learning results are determined and assessed by him. In addition, in contrast to the control carried out by the teacher to test knowledge, skills and abilities, self-control must be carried out by the student during the entire process of his learning.

The task of vocational education is not only the student's ability to develop, to be able to make decisions, to understand the essence of educational activities, but also to master the methods and means of its implementation for subsequent transfer to others [2].

The wording "self-control" means checking, using one's own methods, the results of one's activities, formed competencies, and also being able to adjust the trajectory of educational activities in the direction of improving learning outcomes. In turn, self-control includes the choice of goals and means to obtain the desired result, identifying the causes of shortcomings and their elimination in the process of educational activities, as well as self-analysis of evaluating the results of one's own activities.

The profession of economist is considered one of the most prestigious professions, and for a successful career in this specialty, a graduate of an economics university must be ready for professional self-development and self-education, as well as be able to objectively evaluate the results of their activities. Practice shows that specialists with a high ability for self-improvement and effective organization of their work are more in demand in the labor market. To do this, it is necessary to develop self-control skills in students of economic universities during the process of studying at a university.

Professional training of economists at a university consists not only of acquiring knowledge, but instills the skills to analyze the current economic situation, the ability to defend one's own opinion and foresee the future of decisions made, which, in turn, pushes students to active self-directed cognitive activity.

In other words, the student's ability to independently manage the learning process and correctly evaluate its results is one of the important tasks of higher education.

In order for a student to develop the ability to self-control as a type of independent work, it is necessary to demonstrate and show certain techniques for analysis

using examples, teach how to correctly formulate questions, draw appropriate conclusions, and also be demanding of oneself and be critical of the results of one's work [7].

The main thing here is to instill in the future economist faith in his abilities. It is a well-known fact that, when starting professional activities, graduates often do not dare to take responsibility for solving problems that have arisen, while showing an inability to independently overcome certain difficulties. The solution to this issue, in our opinion, is to develop students' self-control skills, that is, the student must be actively involved in managing their educational process. This will allow you to believe in yourself, in your abilities, critically approach learning results and develop creatively.

An analysis of scientific literature shows that self-control of educational activities, as a problem, arose in parallel with the need to master knowledge and acquire skills.

Indeed, the teacher cannot control the process of assimilation of knowledge without the educational activities of students. A connection is formed between the teacher and the student between the students' self-control and the teacher's control. These two processes, fulfilling their specific functions in the educational process, can complement each other.

This means that the process of control by the teacher is inseparable from the process of self-control by the student. These two components of a single process of personality formation depend on the activity of the student, on the degree of motivation for learning, on the ability to self-control their learning results.

In higher education, control of educational activities is a check of the student's level of mastery of the materials of the academic discipline, and self-control is the student's ability to check his acquired knowledge and make adjustments. At the same time, the teacher can evaluate the effectiveness of the work process and the appropriateness of the introduced adjustments.

A higher school teacher today exercises control over the student's activities. At the same time, the student receives a mark for his work without explanation of the criteria by which the assessment was carried out. Such an assessment system and the student's inability to self-control and self-assessment of learning outcomes does not help the student to really assess their capabilities, which in turn affects the overall learning results and the level of competence development.

Universities began to pay more and more attention to the independent work of students, teaching them to self-educate and constantly improve their level of qualifications. This is primarily due to the fact that less and less time is allocated for classroom training, which naturally leads to a reduction in course material. This means that the student needs to study part of the course independently. This explains the emphasis of universities on students' independent work.

Being able to control one's activities means that a student will manage the process of monitoring one's own educational activities, while acquiring more independence and organization in one's actions.

The curricula of higher educational institutions allocate a significant number of hours for students' independent work, because Assessing the results of one's educational activities is a requirement of the modern educational process. Taking into account the fact that students' professional training is becoming more practice-oriented, this means that the role of students' independent work will also increase. The ability to control one's activities becomes the main indicator of a specialist's professionalism.

One of the important tasks of a student's educational activity is the ability to control and evaluate his educational activities. In addition, in contrast to the control carried out by the teacher to test knowledge, skills and abilities, self-control must be carried out by the student during the entire process of his learning.

The task that universities face today is not only to create the basis for the further development of the student, to teach them to make decisions, to develop the ability to independently evaluate themselves, to understand the content of their activities, but also to find ways, methods and means of its implementation for subsequent transfer them to others.

Thus, modern higher education should develop in students the ability to evaluate the results of educational activities.

It is known that the profession of economist is included in the list of prestigious specialties today. In order to be competitive in the labor market, a graduate of an economics university must have the ability to take a realistic approach to assessing the results of their activities, as well as be ready for professional self-development and self-education.

Practice shows that specialists who know how to improve themselves and master new effective forms of organizing their work are more competitive in the labor market. To do this, it is necessary, in the process of educational activities at a university, to develop in economic students the ability to self-control and self-esteem.

Training specialists at an economics university is not only about gaining knowledge of the relevant profile, but also instilling the skills to analyze the economic situation, defend their point of view and make effective decisions. All this will push the student to manage his cognitive activity [3].

To develop the student's ability to self-control as a type of independent work, one should show with practical examples the techniques used in the course of self-analysis of activities, teach how to accurately pose questions, draw the right conclusions, and also critically evaluate the results of one's educational work.

The main thing is to instill in the future specialist faith in his abilities. As a rule, university graduates who have just started their professional activities do not dare, when unforeseen problems arise at work, to take responsibility for eliminating this problem, while showing their unwillingness to get out of non-standard situations in their professional activities [6].

This problem, from our point of view, can be achieved by developing the student's ability to self-control, involving him in the self-management of his own learning activities, and at the same time instilling

faith in his abilities to develop creatively and be self-critical in the approach to assessing his activities.

An analysis of the scientific literature shows that the need to control the learning process arose in parallel with the need to master knowledge and acquire skills.

Yu.K. Babansky argues that self-control is the ability to independently detect one's mistakes and inaccuracies, as well as find ways to eliminate detected problems [5].

Indeed, in fact, the teacher is not able to control the level of knowledge acquisition without taking into account the results of the student's learning activity, i.e. A connection appears between the teacher and the student in the form of self-control of students and the control of the teacher.

In other words, the process of pedagogical control by the teacher is closely related to the process of self-control by the student. These two processes constitute a unified approach to the formation of an active personality, including the formation of student motivation for education and instilling the ability to self-control their educational activities.

The process of monitoring the educational process is, first of all, establishing the level of mastery of the educational material of the program, and self-control is the student's ability to control and evaluate his acquired knowledge and adjust his own educational process towards improving performance results. In this situation, the teacher can check the level of completion of assignments and work, as well as evaluate the effectiveness of the adjustments introduced into the learning process.

The functions of a teacher at a university include monitoring and analyzing the student's learning process.

In order to develop self-control skills during the educational process, the teacher at each stage of training develops specific tasks for students on the topics of the discipline, selects teaching methods and techniques for better mastery of knowledge, taking into account the student's self-monitoring of their educational results. These tasks are aimed at the ability to realize, understand and analyze the results of one's educational activities, which in turn will contribute to better mastery of educational material [10].

In addition to the functions of organizing and monitoring their own educational activities, future graduates of an economics university and, as a result, also receive the function of managing the educational activities of the teacher. This means that the student will have a need for constant monitoring of the results of his activities, and according to researchers, such graduates have an increased chance of achieving good results in educational activities than students who were under the control of knowledge by the teacher, excluding self-monitoring of their learning results .

If a student is able to monitor his educational results, it means that he will be able to assess the completeness and strength of assimilation of the discipline materials, while identifying gaps in knowledge and finding ways to eliminate them. From a psychological point of view, the student has an incentive to acquire knowledge, because With the help of feedback, he will

be able to check the completed work in the discipline and give a correct assessment of these tasks.

At the same time, self-control also helps the student regulate his behavior in society in accordance with the requirements that exist in society when carrying out certain types of activities, and, therefore, self-control is actions aimed not only at reducing erroneous actions in the learning process and eliminating them, but and on the development of the mental and moral abilities of the individual.

In conditions of an economic crisis, when production is falling and unemployment is high, there is inevitably a need in society for specialists who are able to manage their activities and find non-standard solutions in critical situations [8, 9]. In this regard, the issue of developing self-control skills is of particular importance, since by developing in specialists the skills to control their activities and prevent errors in their work, some economic costs can be avoided.

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